

Plate Layout

SYK PCLS Experiment 3 - October 20, 2025

Plate 1 - 0.1 R406 μ m Treated Plate (500ul of DMSO in 50ml media, 1%DMSO)

ATP D1	ATP D3	ATP D5	Snap (Flex) D1	Snap (Flex) D3	Snap (Flex) D5
ATP D1	ATP D3	ATP D5	Snap (Flex) D1	Snap (Flex) D3	Snap (Flex) D5
FFPE D1	FFPE D3	FFPE D5	Snap (Flex) D1	Snap (Flex) D3	Snap (Flex) D5
FFPE D1	FFPE D3	FFPE D5	Untreated Control FFPE D1	Untreated Control FFPE D3	Untreated Control FFPE D5

Plate 2 - 0.01 R406 μ m Treated Plate (500ul of DMSO in 50ml media, 1%DMSO)

ATP D1	ATP D3	ATP D5	Snap (Flex) D1	Snap (Flex) D3	Snap (Flex) D5
ATP D1	ATP D3	ATP D5	Snap (Flex) D1	Snap (Flex) D3	Snap (Flex) D5
FFPE D1	FFPE D3	FFPE D5	Snap (Flex) D1	Snap (Flex) D3	Snap (Flex) D5
FFPE D1	FFPE D3	FFPE D5	Untreated Control FFPE D1	Untreated Control FFPE D3	Untreated Control FFPE D5

ATP Assay

[ATP]	Luminescence
100	2853820
10	1491387
1	804063
0.1	408320
0.01	211695
0.001	109700.5
0.0001	57300.5
0.00001	29022.5

Results

	[ATP]
Dead Cell	0, 0
Control	0.0041, 0.0011
SB	0.00093, 0.0107
0.1μM R406	0.0083, 0.0015
0.01μM R406	0.025, 0.070

Day 3

Raw Plate Readout

- Temperature at time of reading: 22.2°C

	1	2	blank		dead cell		0.1		0.01		ctrl	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	2279237	2321504		974		4641		197037		135925		454913
B	1232211	1300854		915		1143		258521		54991		329069
C	665347	687830										SB
D	367495	361985										322969
E	185736	182977										272486
F	103108	97620										
G	55829	55177										
H	25515	25438										

Standard Curve

- Background: average of column 4 rows A and B

	1	2	blank		dead cell		0.1		0.01		ctrl	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	2279237	2321504				3696.5		196092.5		134980.5		453968.5
B	1232211	1300854				198.5		257576.5		54046.5		328124.5
C	665347	687830										SB
D	367495	361985										322024.5
E	185736	182977										271541.5
F	103108	97620										
G	55829	55177										
H	25515	25438										
Background	944.5											

[ATP]	Luminescence
100	2300370.5
10	1266532.5
1	676588.5
0.1	364740
0.01	184356.5
0.001	100364
0.0001	55503
0.00001	25476.5

Results

	[ATP]
Dead Cell	0, 0
Control	0.060, 0.038
SB	0.066, 0.060
0.1µM R406	0.0106, 0.032
0.01µM R406	0.0029, 0.00015

Day 5

Raw Plate Readout

- Temperature at time of reading: 22.4°C

				blank	dead cell		0.1		0.01		ctrl		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
A	2653836	2949791		1501		627		385853		151103		202804	Lum
B	1641797	1642523		1223		1514		368921		277852		243163	Lum
C	861282	857075										SB	Lum
D	443568	444791										520688	Lum
E	238130	234016										416686	Lum
F	127803	124895											Lum
G	63656	60987											Lum
H	28260	30634											Lum

Standard Curve

- Background: average of column 4 rows A and B

	1	2	blank		dead cell		0.1		0.01		ctrl		
	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12			
A	2653836	2949791				-735		384491				201442	Lum
B	1641797	1642523				152		367559		276490		241801	Lum
C	861282	857075										SB	Lum
D	443568	444791										519326	Lum
E	238130	234016										415324	Lum
F	127803	124895											Lum
G	63656	60987											Lum
H	28260	30634											Lum
Background	1362												

[ATP]	Luminescence
100	2801814
10	1642160
1	859178.5
0.1	444179.5
0.01	236073
0.001	126349
0.0001	62321.5
0.00001	29447

Results

	[ATP]
Dead Cell	0, 0
Control	0.015, 0.008
SB	0.19, 0.096
0.1μM R406	0.064, 0.057
0.01μM R406	0.002, 0.022

CBA Experiment

Date:

Protocol:

chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj/https://d1spb2x7qk4bg.cloudfront.net/Files/Images/media_assets/pro_detail/datasheets/750000393-human-Inflammation-Panel-1-R5.pdf?v=20250203073815

Spectral Flow:

https://www.biolegend.com/Files/Images/BioLegend/legendplex/instructions/Setup_Procedure_for_Sony_ID7000.pdf

Plate Layout

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	C0	C0	C0	C0	C8	C8	C8	C8	VN D1	VN D1	VN D1	VN D1
B	C1	C1	C1	C1	C9	C9	C9	C9	VN D3	VN D3	VN D3	VN D3
C	C2	C2	C2	C2	C10	C10	C10	C10	VN D5	VN D5	VN D5	VN D5
D	C3	C3	C3	C3	C11	C11	C11	C11				
E	C4	C4	C4	C4	C12	C12	C12	C12				
F	C5	C5	C5	C5	UT D1	UT D1	UT D1	UT D1				
G	C6	C6	C6	C6	UT D3	UT D3	UT D3	UT D3				
H	C7	C7	C7	C7	UT D5	UT D5	UT D5	UT D5				